

4onse: analysis of Four times Open Non-conventional system for Sensing the Environment

Documentation for user, developers, calibration, tutorial

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Partners involved in the work execution

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For more information on the project 4onse, link to <http://www.4onse.ch>

¹ Please start with version number 0.1. Any further minor review will increase the version number by 0.1 while a major review will increase the version by 1.0.

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Executive summary

This document collects the information and guides to build the first official version of the 4onse monitoring system. It contains the full documentation both for the hardware and the software components.

1 Introduction

One of the main project outcomes is the implementation of a royalty-free Environmental Monitoring System (EMS) based on "Open" technologies, including software, hardware, standard and data.

The system is composed by nodes, weather stations, which are connected through the GPRS 2G to the istSOS software hosted on a server dedicated (Figure 1).

Figure 1 – 4onse system schema.

Currently, we developed two versions of the weather station to response to different needs. They are based on the same components, but with different building strategies: the **4onse-mod** uses wires and connectors while **4onse-pcb** uses printed board. The difference is in the way used to connect each component to the other: the first solution (4onse-mod) is a modular solution which maximizes the reproducibility of the system increasing the time spent in building the station; the second (4onse-pcb) is based on a PCB which minimizes the building time increasing the difficulties of the reproducibility.

2 System set-up and installation

This section describes how to set-up the 4onse EMS from the hardware to the software level.

2.1 Hardware layer - Defining the monitoring system

Firstly, the system set-up requires to define the type of monitoring system needed. Basically, there are two kind of systems that can be deployed using the 4onse solution:

- **single-node** solution
- **multi-node** solution

The single-node solution, as the name suggests, is based on a station which is connected to the server. The simple solution needs to respect what concerns the station installation suggestions to get good environmental measures (Table 1).

Sensor	Altitude	Location (suggestions)
Temperature/humidity	from 1.7 to 2 m	A green field at least 10 meters away from any kind of obstacle (buildings, trees, etc.)
Pluviometer	from 1.5 to 2 m	10 meters away from any kind of obstacle which can prevent the rain to fall inside the bucket
Solar radiation	2 m	At the top of the pole, pay attention to possible shadows which can make shade on the sensor
Anemometer	2/2.5 m	At the top of the pole and at least 10 meters away from possible obstacles

Table 1 – Installation suggestion for the deployment of a station in suburban areas.

The multi-node solution is composed by two or more stations which are connected to the data warehouse. For the selection of the stations' location in a basin, some factors can be considered:

- areas located closer to the sub-basins' centroids;
- areas with considerably high rainfall;
- accessibility – closer to a main road
- security
- at least one station for each sub-basin

Secondly, for the deployment of the 4nse weather station you can choose between the two solutions developed: the 4nse-mod or the 4nse-pcb. If you are planning to implement a multi-node system, both the stations can be deployed together since they are totally independent to each other. There is a one-to-one connection between the node and the server, the weather station and the istSOS.

Thirdly, defined the previous points, the development and implementation of the hardware, communication and service layer can start.

2.2 Service layer – The server requirements

The service layer is the data warehouse of the system. It requires:

- a server infrastructure
- a public IP or domain name which must be accessible through the Internet

The Operating System (OS) suggested is a Debian based distribution which is open source and totally compliant with the philosophy of the project. Ubuntu 16.04 LTS is suggested since it is the most tested distribution during the project activities. Since the software selected for the 4nse EMS are open source and cross-platform, other OS can be used for this purpose if they guarantee the royalty free and open strategy chosen.

The hardware requirements are dependent to the type of network implemented. The 4nse EMS will have more than 30 nodes and no issue on server side were detected during the testing period in terms of downtime or stress caused by overloading requests, keeping a good level of Quality of Service. Hereinafter the server specifications:

- two CPUs of @ 2 GHz 64 bits

- 2 GB of RAM
- 200 GB of Hard Disk SSD

Once the server architecture is prepared, the required software to run the 4nse application to manage the data (istSOS) are:

- PostgreSQL >= 9.3 PostGIS
- Apache
- Python 2.7

2.3 Communication layer – Data transmission

The transmission of the data is based on GPRS 2G mobile connection. To enable the communication, the station mounts a SIM800 board which needs a SIM card from a mobile provider to work. The choice of the provider is balanced between two main factors:

1. good mobile signal to guarantee a stable connection to the Internet;
2. price of the flat plan.

The free android application OpenSignal (<https://opensignal.com/>) is useful to get the signal strength stats of the providers available at the station's location. The RSSI dBm must be up to -80 dBm to have a stable connection between the SIM800 and the nearest phone cell.

RSSI dBm	Condition	-91	OK	-71	Excellent
-109	Marginal	-89	OK	-69	Excellent
-107	Marginal	-87	OK	-67	Excellent
-105	Marginal	-85	OK	-65	Excellent
-103	Marginal	-83	Good	-63	Excellent
-101	Marginal	-81	Good	-61	Excellent
-99	Marginal	-79	Good	-59	Excellent
-97	Marginal	-77	Good	-57	Excellent
-95	Marginal	-75	Good	-55	Excellent
-93	OK	-73	Excellent	-53	Excellent

The connection between the SIM800 and the cell is possible thanks to the Access Point Name (APN) settings provided by the mobile provider. Usually only the APN is needed to establish a connection, but in some cases the APN user and the PIN code are required.

3 Calibration and system validation

The system validation analysis is suggested before starting with the deployment activity to check the data quality, the system durability and the data transmission stability. Since the 4nse weather stations are not industrially distributed, the building process, due to the user, could have some differences in some components, like for example the weather radiation shield. Nevertheless, the 4nse prototypes, as described in the user documentation, were tested and validated showing very high values of correlation (see D2.4) by means of comparing the time series with an official weather station of the hydro-meteorological network of the Cantone Ticino in Switzerland.

3.1 The reference station

The weather station built should be compared with a nearby authoritative weather station to validate and analyse the correlation between the time series of the parameters measured (air temperature, air humidity, air pressure, cumulated rain, etc.). The following methods are useful to have a good estimation of the data quality:

- visual comparison of the recorded data;
- time series goodness-of-fit calculation through the coefficient of determination by Pearson;
- coherence of aggregated values (daily mean, max and min values);
- scatter plots to evaluate the general behaviour of the 4onse weather sensors;
- probability density function to validate the residuals distribution.

3.2 Python tools for data analysis

Many are the tools available to perform time series analysis. During the project activities, some were selected to respect the Openness principle of the project:

- Observations Analysis Tools (OAT)
- Pandas
- Matplotlib

3.3 Rain gauge calibration

The rain gauge Davis AeroCone 6465, selected to measure the cumulated water, has screws under aerodynamic funnel for each chamber. The tipping bucket can be accurately tuned and calibrated thanks to a special bottle mounted over the rain gauge and filled with a known quantity of water. The accuracy is strongly affected by the rain gauge installation which must be perfectly in level to avoid errors related to a non-equilibrated balance.

For the calibration, a bottle with 53.5 cl of water, which is equal to 25 mm of rain and 125 tips, should be prepared. The tipping bucket is considered calibrated when the tips measured are between 118.75 and 131.25 (5% error).

For an in-depth description please refer to the deliverable D2.3.

4 User documentation

The user documentation is available at the following link:

<http://www.4onse.ch/docs/html/>

The linked website, attached to the document as a zipped archive, begins with an overview of the project and of the 4onse solution developed. Then, the installation procedure of the two stations is described in two different ways:

- the 4onse-mod station through a step by step tutorial from the weather station installation to the code uploading and to the synchronization with the istSOS;
- the 4onse-pcb with a word document.

5 Developer documentation

The developer documentation is available at the following link:

<http://4onse.ch/docs/lib/>

The istSOS communication library developed to enable the synchronization between the weather station and the istSOS was described to make easy the understanding of the classes implemented and functions provided. The external developers are invited to contribute in the development of the library by making suggestion, opening issues or forking the repository to add improvements and correct bugs.

6 Tutorials and hand-outs

During the first year and a half many workshops were prepared and attended by participants in conferences and meetings with stakeholders. The material was collected and organized in a website:

<http://istsos.org/en/trunk/doc/tutorial.html>

The tutorials are mainly oriented to:

- How to install istSOS
- Description of the main functionalities of istSOS
- How to access data
- How to map sensors
- Two small tutorials on how to connect sensors to Arduino boards
- How to manage security features within the data warehouse